

The Effect of Idealistic Advertisements Contrasted with Authentic Advertisements on the Self Concept of Women: A Study to Grasp the Target Audience's Attentiveness

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ABSTRACT

In an age where the existence of advertisements adorning several evolutionary forms has become an indispensable component, is where print media still continues to consume a sizeable proportion of the consumer's attention. The study attempted to investigate the underlying insecurities that ultimately leads to a lower self-concept on part of the consumer, a medication to which, can prove to be an opportunity for the advertising industry to produce a better advertising ethos benefitting the brand and the consumer in terms of higher profitability and brand loyalty.

An experimental design is embodied in the study exploring the influence of existing advertisements on the self-concept of women forming a colossal consumer base for the apparel and cosmetic industry which uses advertising in fashion magazines as a primary method of communication. An evident use of idealistic imagery and unrealistic expectations has been shelled on the consumer. This is paired in difference with an 'experiment advertisement' which has been solely created for the study with a realistic demeanour in terms of the zilch editing. To avoid an unrealistic enhancement of the product, involving a realistic female model and focusing on portraying an image the target audience feels a kinship with to assess the influence it has on the users of the product. Previous studies have only explored the issue of poor self-concept but have had limited exploration of the satisfaction that a realistic advertisement can bring about. A higher consumer's self-concept and brand loyalty can be exceedingly encouraging for the brand in the market as well as the advertising industry to evolve in terms of its thresholds of standards.

1. Introduction

In India's liberalized and globalized economy, the biggest concern of advertisers lies in making advertising the most effective, which is how well the company is able to achieve the intended. Advertising effectiveness to a great extent is dependent on the trial of the product, the pictorial and verbal components in the advertisement, the competitors advertising strategies, and length of the advertisement. However, websites are skimmed in a very short span of 15 seconds and under whereas print reading material becomes a lot more engaging for consumers. (Alshaali, Varshney, 2005). Fashion has been conceived as somewhat of an oppression that is hegemonic in nature that shoves a sense of conformity amongst the women population (Wolf, 1991). Images released in the fashion world lead to enormous dissatisfaction in women because of the unrealistic imagery that leads to expectations making most women feel inferior. (Lakoff, Scherr, 1984). It is found that for promoting unrealistic expectations of being thin, women's fashion magazines are the biggest influencers. (Thompson and Heinberg, 1999). A relatively smaller portion of readers develop eating disorders but generations of women feel anxiety and body image issues over weight. (Kilbourne, 1995). There is a lot of evidence from the body of literature that shows how being exposed to thin body images and an idealistic body through the media causes a disturbance in body perception of women and make themselves think they are heavier than what they actually are (Groesz, Levine veMurnen, 2002; Cusumanove Thompson, 2001). Body perception is a big issue in adolescence where

young individuals are extremely sensitive about their appearance and are very susceptible to having disturbed body images. This can lead to anxiousness and change in patterns of eating leading to eating disorders. (Wykes and Gunter, 2004). A positive body image serves as a strong support for psychology and female university students in the UK and protects them from accepting thin idealised body images. (Halliwell 2013).

A trend of a concern for the low self-esteem from an individual level to a societal concern has emerged in the last few decades. The North American society has accepted that a high self-esteem is extremely desirable and it is part of the central psychology from where all the positive behaviours and outcomes emerge. Low self-esteem has been found to the root of individual and societal problems leading to dysfunction. (Baumeister, Campbell, Krueger, Vohs, 2003) The focus of diagnosis has shifted from complex measures to simple self-reporting measures. The National Eating Disorder Association (2005) defines body image as what one observes whilst coming across a mirror or what is experienced or imagines about the physical appearances which includes components of weight, height, body shape, assumptions, generalizations, and memories. It's the mental imagery one makes of oneself. Body image is the self-created mental image but may not be congruent to the reality to other's perception. It strongly influences the behaviour (Psychology Today). Most Studies have been conducted to check the effect of these advertisements after exposure. No studies were found to

conduct body image together to get a comprehensive understanding of the existing score. Future studies might use protocol measures to assess feelings toward self and brands as viewers watch - or immediately after they watch - sample ads. More basic studies might investigate effects of self-esteem appeals on advertising recall, brand awareness (Durgee, 1986). The cross-cultural perspective on examining the influence of ideal imagery should be examined. The negative portrayals of females in advertising has become a controversial issue of an international stature. (Norris, Colman 1992). The influence of ideal body images and retouching of images have mostly left a negative impact on women but this cannot be generalized as most studies have been conducted on adolescents and college going women. A study needs to be conducted on women from different age groups and their susceptibility to the advertisements of beauty, fashion and accessories which are found in fashion magazines. (Smeesters, Mussweiler, Mandel, 2010). The study was the first to show that advertisements featuring a thin, attractive female model in a magazine, resulted in a higher self-objectification in comparison to control advertisements used in the study. As foreseen by Fredrickson and Roberts (1997), by viewing this kind of advertisement featuring "ideal images" compels women to ponder about their physical appearance and critiquing themselves. Women begin to describe and see themselves in a different light after being exposed to these advertisements as the body and image becomes a crucial point of reference. In this study, self-objectification was used as a variable which has higher scope of further investigation. The results of this study however, was derived from a sample of young, Australian, college-educated females majorly of European descent. (Harper, Tiggemann, 2008).

It is observed that the self-esteem of a woman prior to completing the survey is bound to have an impact on the level of self-esteem that is recorded after observing the stimulus or images shown. In addition, it was gathered that women whose bodies do not fall in the category of the "ideal" body type by society, tend to believe that their bodies are not ideal either; rather they strive to resemble a body type that is unlike their own and is considered ideal by society. Future research has scope of focusing on the fragile relationship between the images portrayed by media of "thin ideal" body type and that of college women's self-esteem. (Sheehan, 2013) Lesser studies were found to have used unseen advertisements to avoid an existing bias using advertisements with realistic images. It has come to be a point where women themselves find thin, long-legged models with perfect skin attractive but the preference goes to untouched and authentic image. The research shows that the basic understanding of body dissatisfaction by working with body satisfaction which can be remarkably improved when subjects, along with manipulated images see a restored and authentic version. (Reaves, Hitchon, Park, Yun, 2004)

2. Method

a) Sample

The Sample chosen for this particular study were women from age group of 21 to 50 who have the minimum educational qualification of being graduates and are regular subscribers to fashion magazines and consumers of products advertised in these magazines. The sample size for the first part of the study

that involved testing the advertising effectiveness was 15 and the sample size for the second part of the study that involved the actual experiment was also 15. The study follows an experimental module due to which a larger sample was not feasible to work with. Each subject completed the experiment in about four hours.

b) Methodology

The study undertaken is of an experimental nature comprising the following elements and a progression of the following measures:

1. The Stimulus: The chief element used as the stimulus for the study is advertisements of the product category of women's denims and lipstick. They were divided into two sets which are as follows:
 - i. Existing advertisements of denims and lipstick featuring female models which have graced the Indian market. A careful attempt was made to not choose the very popular brands of denims or lipsticks and were replaced by lesser known brands in order to avoid a consumer bias that may percolate in the minds of the respondent when they are exposed to the stimulus.
 - ii. Experimental advertisements of women's denims and lipstick were constructed for the purpose of the study wherein, the model was chosen on the basis of a more regular appearance and as a user of the product. The idea behind this stimulus was to keep the image as realistic as possible. A professional photo shoot was done for making the advertisements. Canon 5D was used for this purpose along with editing software like Photoshop and Illustrator for the creation of the advertisement. However, no postproduction editing or highlighting was done to the model and entirety of the original image of the product as well as the model was preserved.
2. The Design: The authentic design of the experiment was conducted in the following stages:
 - i. The obvious progression after the design of the experiment advertisements were to evaluate the effectiveness. This step was not necessary for the existing advertisements as the evaluation of effectiveness of the advertisements has already been done before it was launched into the market. On the contrary, the experiment advertisements needed a concrete basis to stand before being projected into the experiment.
 - ii. Four advertisements of denims were divided into two categories named J.1 and J.2 for the convenience of the research.
 - iii. Two advertisements of lipstick were divided into two categories named L.1 and L.2 for the convenience of the research.
 - iv. An advertising effectiveness questionnaire was administered to a sample of 15 women, exposing them to each category of the print advertisement.

They answered the questionnaire based on what they saw, registered and recalled.

- v. The next stage of the experiment was conducted using the most effective category of advertisements from J.1 and J.2 for denim category and L.1 and L.2 for lipstick category.
- vi. Robson's SCQ questionnaire was first administered on a sample of 15 women. A few days later, they were exposed to existing advertisements and again the self-concept questionnaire was administered. Again, after a few days they were shown the experimental advertisements and asked to fill up the self concept questionnaire.

c) Instruments

1. Advertising Effectiveness Questionnaire

The questionnaire was essentially an advertising effectiveness questionnaire already validated but for the benefit of the study, we added certain elements for a better evaluation of the effectiveness. The reliability was tested on of the same questionnaires on both the categories of advertisements. Ostensibly, the Chronbach alpha value for J.1 was 0.809 and for J.2 was 0.785 displaying the strength of the internal consistency of the instrument is satisfactory. The Chronbach alpha value for L.1 was 0.586 which is not satisfactory and for L.2 was 0.894 displaying the strength of the internal consistency of the instrument is satisfactory.

2. Robson's Self Concept Questionnaire

For the purpose of this study, an established questionnaire with a scoring key was used. This has been used extensively and is a reliable scale to assess self-concept.

3. Results and Discussion

Stage 1

The sample was shown advertisements under the category of J.1 and J.2 and L.1 and L.2 in a print format. This was followed by them answering a questionnaire about the two categories of advertisements of two product categories respectively. The questionnaire comprised items that would assess the advertising effectiveness of the advertisement. The objective was to use the most effective advertisement category in the study.

A comparison using the statistical tool of paired t test was conducted between the two questionnaires to assess which category was more effective. Observation made from the Sample Paired T Test states that in the denim advertisement comparison, J.2 category of advertisement is more effective than J.1. Examination of the paired samples highlights the mean

of J.2 is higher than J.1 and in the case of reverse coded items, the mean of J.2 is lower than that of J.1. In the cosmetic section, L.2 is more effective than L.1

Stage 2

As per the observations made from the paired sample T test, there is a difference between the original score of self-concept and the one recorded after exposure to existing advertisements. There is a decrease in the score after the exposure from 2.07 to 1.80.

Stage 3

As per the observations made from the paired sample T test, there is a significant difference between the score after exposure to existing ads and the one recorded after exposure to experiment (realistic) advertisements. There is an increase in the score after the exposure to the experiment advertisements from 1.80 to 2.47.

Stage 4

As per the observations made from the paired sample T test, there is a significant difference between the original score and the one recorded after exposure to experimental (realistic) advertisements as the P value is .003. There is an increase in the score after the exposure as the mean value now was found to be 2.47.

4. Conclusion

There happens to be very little research about the positive reinforcement of realistic images in the advertising industry and the effect it has on the target audience. As, we can see from the results of the experiment study, women's body image score significantly goes down when exposed to the existing (unrealistic) advertisements as the surreal imagery makes them feel insecure about their own appearance. Whereas, after exposure to the experiment (realistic) advertisements, their self-concept score increases and they feel more confident with themselves as the advertisement acts as a positive fortification and helps the target audience identify themselves with the advertisements made specifically for the study.

There is a huge opportunity for the advertising industry to tap into this market where a potential customer can be converted to a brand loyal by the communication that is provided by the advertisement of that company. The customer with a feeling on contentment, satisfaction and the validation provided by the advertisement using a realistic image will not only leave an economic advantage for the advertiser but also a moral profit on the consciences.

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